

Development and initial evaluation of a combustion-based sample introduction system for direct isotopic analysis of mercury in solid samples via multi-collector ICP-mass spectrometry

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ABSTRACT

High-precision isotopic analysis of mercury (Hg) using multi-collector ICP-mass spectrometry (MC-ICP-MS) is a powerful method for obtaining insight into the sources, pathways and sinks of this toxic metal. Modification of a commercially available mercury analyzer (Teledyne Leeman Labs, Hydra IIc – originally designed for quantification of Hg through sample combustion, collection of the Hg vapor on a gold amalgamator, subsequent controlled release of Hg and detection using CVAAS) enabled the system to be used for the direct high-precision Hg isotopic analysis of solid samples using MC-ICP-MS – *i.e.*, without previous sample digestion and subsequent dilution. The changes made to the mercury analyzer did not compromise its (simultaneous) use for Hg quantification via CVAAS. The Hg gas was mixed with a Tl-containing aerosol produced via pneumatic nebulization, creating wet plasma conditions, and enabling the use of Tl as an internal standard for correction of instrumental mass discrimination. Accurate and precise (0.10 ‰ 2SD, $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$, n=5) results were obtained for an in-house standard solution of Hg (20 ng Hg sample intake). Initial validation relied on the successful analysis of two solid certified reference materials of biological origin (BCR CRM 464 Tuna fish and NRC-CNRC TORT-3 Lobster hepatopancreas). It was shown that instrumental mass discrimination can be adequately corrected for by relying on the use of an aqueous Hg standard solution (NIST SRM 3133), without the need of matrix-matching. The novel setup developed thus allows for direct high-precision isotopic analysis of Hg in solid samples, thus enhancing the sample throughput. It is also suited for samples for which low amounts are available only and/or that are characterized by low Hg concentrations.

KEYWORDS

Mercury, isotopic analysis, multi-collector ICP-mass spectrometry, solid samples, sample combustion

1. Introduction

Mercury (Hg) occurs naturally, but emissions of this toxic metal due to anthropogenic activities contribute to a much larger extent to its levels in the environment [1]. Mercury undergoes bioaccumulation and biomagnification, which raises concern due to its toxicity to humans and wildlife [2]. It is involved in a complex biogeochemical cycle involving various environmental compartments and is distributed worldwide due to its ability for travelling long distances through the atmosphere. Therefore, a more profound understanding of the sources, sinks and pathways of Hg is of the utmost importance [3]. Isotopic analysis of Hg is considered as an important tool to better understand this biogeochemical cycling [4,5], complementing the information obtained via determination of the total Hg (THg) concentration and speciation analysis [6].

Mercury has seven stable isotopes: ^{196}Hg (0.15%), ^{198}Hg (9.97%), ^{199}Hg (16.87%), ^{200}Hg (23.10%), ^{201}Hg (13.18%), ^{202}Hg (29.86%) and ^{204}Hg (6.87%), and is one of the few elements for which both mass-dependent and mass-independent isotope fractionation (MDF and MIF) occurs. While in MDF, the isotope fractionation is caused by the difference in mass between the isotopes considered, other factors, such as the size of the nucleus and/or its magnetic properties govern MIF [8,9]. The combination of MDF and MIF of the different Hg isotopes provides a multi-dimensional approach to identify sources and study biogeochemical pathways of Hg in different sample types [10].

Investigation of the natural variations in the isotopic composition of Hg is carried out using multi-collector ICP-mass spectrometry (MC-ICP-MS). Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometry (TIMS) is not suitable for isotopic analysis of Hg due to the high vapor pressure and ionization energy of this element. MC-ICP-MS offers an excellent isotope ratio precision (down to 0.001% RSD under ideal circumstances), but instrumental mass discrimination [11] needs to be adequately corrected for. As the extent of mass discrimination is affected by the matrix composition, traditionally the analyte needs to be isolated from the matrix prior to isotopic analysis. As also the analyte concentration affects the extent of mass discrimination, samples and standards are typically closely concentration-matched. Different approaches are used to correct for mass discrimination [12]. For Hg isotopic analysis, reliable mass bias correction has been obtained via the combination of (i) internal correction based on the use of a Tl isotopic standard (NIST SRM 997) and relying on the Russell equation and (ii) external correction based on the use of a Hg isotopic standard (NIST SRM 3133) measured in a sample-standard bracketing (SSB) approach [13].

The most widely used sample introduction system for Hg isotopic analysis is cold vapor generation (CVG) [14]. CVG-ICP-MS enables accurate and precise routine Hg isotopic analysis at concentration levels down to $1\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Hg. CVG provides a very high analyte introduction efficiency owing to the highly efficient reaction between Hg(II) and SnCl_2 (no additional fractionation is induced), and leads to stable and

continuous Hg⁺ signals (continuous flow). In addition, previous chromatographic isolation of Hg from the sample matrix can be avoided as a result of the selectivity of the reaction between Hg(II) and SnCl₂. By using this setup, Hg isotopic analysis can be accomplished with a precision down to 0.10‰ (2SD) for δ²⁰²Hg [15,16]. However, CVG requires the introduction of aqueous solutions and needs the mercury to be present as Hg²⁺, thus necessitating complete mineralization of the sample of interest or quantitative extraction of the analyte out of the sample matrix. The typical sample preparation approach for Hg isotopic analysis of solid samples is (microwave-assisted) wet acid digestion. Samples containing relatively high Hg concentrations (i.e., ≥ 25 ng g⁻¹) can be analyzed by CVG-MC-ICP-MS, since these can be acid digested with excellent Hg recovery and be subsequently diluted to adequate Hg (1 – 5 ng mL⁻¹) and acid (< 20%, v/v) concentrations [17]. This approach shows some limitations, as also a (large) fraction of the matrix is solubilized in the acid digestion, this may inhibit Hg²⁺ reduction in the CVG and affect CVG washout characteristics, potentially biasing Hg isotope ratio measurements [18].

The situation becomes even more challenging for samples with lower concentrations of Hg (< 25 ng g⁻¹). Even with 100% recovery, the dilution of acid concentrations to < 20% would cause very low Hg concentrations (i.e., < 1 ng mL⁻¹), rendering Hg isotopic analysis difficult [17]. Very recently, Faraday cup amplifiers with a 10¹³ Ω resistor have become available, and in combination with a high-efficiency interface and the use of dry plasma conditions, accurate and precise Hg isotope ratio measurements were demonstrated at concentration levels down to 0.1 ng mL⁻¹ [19]. But even then, some samples are not yet amenable to high-precision CVG-MC-ICP-MS analysis. Therefore, various offline pre-concentration approaches have been developed to overcome this limitation and pre-concentrate Hg to appropriate levels (≥ 1 ng mL⁻¹ Hg); these include gold trapping, activated carbon trapping, KMnO₄ + H₂SO₄ trapping, combustion (or pyrolysis) followed by acid trapping and chromatographic preconcentration [18, 20-26]. These preconcentration methods do allow Hg isotopic analysis of many samples containing low Hg concentrations only, but still, the limited amount of sample available may hinder the analysis. In addition, these methods are time-consuming, rely on the use of sometimes hazardous chemicals and pose a risk of Hg isotope fractionation due to Hg loss (or contamination) during the different preparation steps.

In this work, a novel method allowing for direct isotopic analysis of Hg in solid samples without any prior sample treatment has been developed. This was achieved by modifying a commercially available Hg combustion analyzer based on trapping of Hg vapor on a gold amalgamator and detection using cold vapor atomic absorption spectroscopy (CVAAS) for enabling its coupling to an MC-ICP-MS instrument..

2. Experimental

2.1. Instrumentation

For direct isotopic analysis of Hg, a Teledyne Leeman Labs (USA) Hydra IIc mercury combustion analyzer was coupled to a Thermo Fisher Scientific (Germany) Neptune *Plus* MC-ICP-MS instrument (**Figure 1**) following modification. When using the Hydra IIc for Hg quantification, solid or liquid samples are introduced into a pyrolysis (combustion) furnace in a nickel or quartz boat. The sample is subjected to drying and pyrolysis heating steps to remove solvents and organic matter while introducing an O₂ flow. All gases generated pass through a heated catalyst furnace to remove halogens, nitrous oxides and sulfur oxides, while the remaining species are carried through a Nafion® dryer to remove water vapor before reaching a gold trap, where the analyte is collected as Hg⁰ by amalgamation. Subsequently, the gold trap is heated to release the Hg⁰ in gaseous form, which is then transported by the O₂ flow to the spectrometer for detection of the total Hg elemental content based on AAS detection (measuring the intensity at the Hg primary atomic line at 253.7 nm). The transient signal is measured in series in a high-sensitivity cell followed by a low-sensitivity one.

In this work, the Hydra IIc unit and its operating conditions were modified to combine quantification of Hg via AAS and its subsequent introduction into the MC-ICP-MS instrument for high-precision isotopic analysis. These Hg isotope ratio measurements were carried out using a Thermo Fisher Scientific (Germany) Neptune *Plus* multi-collector (MC-ICP-MS) instrument, equipped with nine Faraday cups. Coupling was accomplished using flexible Tygon® tubing and use of the set-up thus obtained necessitated some modifications, enabling switching between O₂ and Ar for purging the unit to fully remove the gases generated during the combustion phase and transporting the Hg⁰ generated upon heating the Au amalgamator into the MC-ICP-MS instrument in an Ar carrier gas flow.. The Hg⁰-loaded gas flow coming from the Hydra IIc was admixed in a “T-piece” with a wet aerosol of Tl generated using a 100 μL min⁻¹ concentric nebulizer fitted onto a dual spray chamber, consisting of a cyclonic and a Scott-type sub-unit.

To ensure a smooth and reproducible gas switching process, a setup using three 3-way solenoid valves with Teflon bodies controlled by in-house software was designed. A scheme of the electronics and a picture of the device designed in-house can be found in **Figure S1**. The setup automatically switches between the three different operating conditions required for successful direct isotopic analysis of Hg using the Hydra IIc as a sample introduction system for MC-ICP-MS, as illustrated in **Figure 2**. These steps include:

- (1) sample decomposition and Hg collection (**Figure 2A**)

The three electrical valves are initially positioned such to prevent combustion gases from entering the MC-ICP-MS instrument (V2), while supplying O₂ to the Hydra IIc (V1) and Ar to the ICP (V3). Sample

decomposition occurs at high temperature, and the evading Hg vapor is collected through amalgamation with gold.

(2) purging of combustion gases (**Figure 2B**)

O₂ gas is purged by switching V1 and the furnace is swept with an Ar flow. Combustive gases are removed through the exhaust exit (V2), preventing their entrance into the ICP. An extended waiting time is used to ensure full removal of O₂ and the combustion gases. During both steps 1 and 2, Ar is supplied to the ICP to maintain plasma stability and minimize changes when switching between gas sources.

(3) transfer of Hg⁰ to the MC-ICP-MS instrument (**Figure 2C**)

V2 and V3 are sequentially switched to establish the connection between the Hydra IIc and the ICP. Hg desorption takes place through heating of the amalgamator. Gaseous Hg⁰ is transported using the Ar flow and mixed with the wet aerosol containing the Tl internal standard generated via pneumatic nebulization. During this step, a transient Hg signal is obtained through sequential AAS and MC-ICP-MS monitoring.

After analyzing a sample, all valves were switched to the original positions again, thus restoring the initial conditions.

Table 1 shows the operating conditions and data acquisition parameters of the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS coupling. **Table 2** provides an overview of the different steps required for successful Hg isotopic analysis using this set-up. The operating principle of the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS coupling is described into more detail in the Supplementary Material.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a mercury combustion analyzer coupled as an on-line solid sample introduction system to an MC-ICP-MS unit for high-precision isotopic analysis of Hg. Pneumatic nebulization was used for the introduction of Tl as an internal standard to correct for instrumental mass discrimination and to achieve wet plasma conditions.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the operating principle of the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS combination. The steps include: (A) combustion and Hg trapping, (B) purging of the Hydra IIc with Ar gas, and (C) detection of Hg through AAS and MC-ICP-MS. (printed in B/W in the printed journal)

Table 1. Instrument settings and data acquisition parameters of the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS combination.

Hydra IIc						
Oxygen flow rate (mL min ⁻¹)	250					
Drying temperature (°C)	100					
Drying time (s)	60					
Decomposition temperature (°C)	800					
Decomposition time (s)	150					
Waiting time (s)	120					
Catalyst temperature (°C)	700					
Desorption temperature (°C)	800					
Desorption time (s)	30					
Neptune Plus MC-ICP-MS						
Cup configuration						
L3	L2	L1	C	H1	H2	H3
¹⁹⁸ Hg	¹⁹⁹ Hg	²⁰⁰ Hg	²⁰¹ Hg	²⁰² Hg	²⁰³ Tl	²⁰⁵ Tl
10 ¹¹ Ω	10 ¹¹ Ω	10 ¹¹ Ω	10 ¹¹ Ω	10 ¹¹ Ω	10 ¹² Ω	10 ¹² Ω
Instrumental parameters						
RF power (W)	1200-1300					
Cool gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	13					
Auxiliary gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.70					
Nebulizer gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.20					
Carrier gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.20					
Additional gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.50					
Uptake rate for Tl solution (mL min ⁻¹)	0.17					
Sampling cone	Ni					
Skimmer cone	Ni, H-type					
Resolution	Low resolution					
Mode	Static mode					
Integration time (s)	0.275					
Acquisition time (s)	100					
Total analysis time per sample (s)	500					

Table 2. Overview of the different steps required for using the Hydra IIc as an on-line sample introduction system for high-precision isotopic analysis of Hg via MC-ICP-MS.

	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3
Hydra IIc processes	Sample combustion/Hg trapping	Waiting time	Hg desorption
Valve 1	Off	On	On
Valve 2	Off	Off	On
Valve 3	Off	Off	On
Gas Hydra-IIc	O ₂	Ar	Ar
Destination sample gas	Exhaust V2	Exhaust V2	MC-ICP-MS
Sample gas	-	-	Ar (0.20 L min ⁻¹)
Spare 1 gas	Ar (0.20 L min ⁻¹)	Ar (0.20 L min ⁻¹)	-
Spare 2 gas	Ar (0.50 L min ⁻¹)	Ar (0.50 L min ⁻¹)	Ar (0.50 L min ⁻¹)
Analysis stage	Sample decomposition/Hg preconcentration (Au amalgamation)	Hydra-IIc purging	Hg ⁰ transfer

2.2. Reagents and standards

High-purity water (resistivity >18.2 MΩ cm) was obtained from a Milli-Q Element water purification system (Millipore, France), while pro-analysis 14 M HNO₃ (ChemLab, Belgium) was further purified by sub-boiling distillation using a Savillex (USA) DST acid purification system.

A single-element standard solution of Hg (1 g L⁻¹; Instrument Solutions, The Netherlands) was appropriately diluted and used for method development and Hg quantification.

Isotopic reference materials of Hg (NIST SRM 3133) and Tl (NIST SRM 997) were appropriately diluted and used for external and internal correction for instrumental mass discrimination, respectively.

2.3. Samples and sample preparation

A previously characterized in-house (IH) standard solution of Hg (Inorganic Ventures, The Netherlands, Lot: F2-HG02105) was used for optimization, method development, and validation purposes in the context of isotopic analysis of Hg [16]. This standard was also used for assessing the accuracy and precision in Hg isotope ratio measurements. Furthermore, two reference materials of biological origin, BCR CRM 464

(Tuna fish) and NCR-CNRC TORT-3 (Lobster hepatopancreas), were used for initial validation of the approach developed.

When using the Hydra IIc as a sample introduction system for both quantification and isotopic analysis of Hg, no sample pre-treatment was required at all. A sample amount containing ca. 20 ng of THg was weighed (or pipetted for aqueous solutions) and directly added into a pre-cleaned nickel sample boat prior to analysis. In the case of analyzing aqueous standard solutions, the nickel boat was filled with diatomaceous earth to minimize issues during the drying and pyrolysis heating steps.

2.4. Data processing

To calculate the Hg isotope ratios from the transient signals produced by the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS set-up, three different approaches were compared: (i) point-by-point (PbP) evaluation, (ii) peak area integration (PAI), and (iii) use of a linear regression slope (LRS). A detailed description of these various methods for calculating isotope ratios from transient signals can be found elsewhere [27, 28].

The bias caused by instrumental mass discrimination was corrected for using a combination of internal correction using the Russell equation with Tl as admixed internal standard (NIST SRM 997 - Tl) and external correction with NIST SRM 3133 Hg as the external standard measured in a sample-standard bracketing (SSB) approach [29-31]. To ensure accurate results, the Hg signal intensities were matched (within $\pm 10\%$). No blank subtraction was performed because the effect of the blank was shown to be negligible within the experimental precision.

MDF was expressed in delta notation ($\delta^{xxx}\text{Hg} \text{‰}$) relative to the NIST SRM 3133 external standard [14], following equation 1:

$$\delta^{xxx}\text{Hg}(\text{‰}) = \left(\frac{\left(\frac{^{xxx}\text{Hg}}{^{198}\text{Hg}} \right)}{\left(\frac{^{xxx}\text{Hg}}{^{198}\text{Hg}} \right)_{\text{NIST SRM 3133}}} - 1 \right) \times 1000 \quad (1)$$

where XXX = 199, 200, 201 or 202.

MIF was reported in capital delta notation ($\Delta^{xxx}\text{Hg} \text{‰}$) and was calculated from the corresponding measured $\delta^{xxx}\text{Hg}$ values using equation 2 – 4 [14]:

$$\Delta^{199}\text{Hg} = \delta^{199}\text{Hg} - (\delta^{202}\text{Hg} \times 0.2520) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta^{200}\text{Hg} = \delta^{200}\text{Hg} - (\delta^{202}\text{Hg} \times 0.5024) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta^{201}\text{Hg} = \delta^{201}\text{Hg} - (\delta^{202}\text{Hg} \times 0.7520) \quad (4)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Hydra IIc as a sample introduction system

For evaluating the efficiency of Hg transfer between the Hydra IIc and MC-ICP-MS instrument, peak intensity values obtained using AAS detection were compared to those obtained using MC-ICP-MS. Despite comparing signal intensities in a narrow range (RSD = 6%, n=14), a clear linear correlation ($R^2 = 0.95$) was observed between the results obtained using the Hydra IIc and MC-ICP-MS detectors (see **Figure S2**). This suggests efficient and reproducible Hg transfer throughout the process and suggests the possibility of using the AAS detector for a preliminary assessment of the Hg content in unknown samples prior to high-precision isotopic analysis. Such evaluation is essential to ensure adequate matching of analyte content between sample and standard, as avoiding a signal intensity mismatch exceeding 10% is often required for successful mass bias correction.

In this context, an experiment was carried out to ensure the reliability of the Hydra IIc for Hg quantification after the modifications made. The reference materials BCR CRM 464 (Tuna fish) and NCR-CNRC TORT-3 (Lobster hepatopancreas) were analyzed, and the results were found to be in good agreement with the reference values ($t_{\text{experimental}} < t_{\text{critical}}$), with recoveries (n = 3) of $99\% \pm 5\%$ and $105\% \pm 10\%$, respectively.

Additional experiments were also carried out for initial assessment of the performance of the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS combination. **Figure 3A** illustrates that doubling the amount of Hg introduced into the Hydra IIc (20 ng and 40 ng Hg) resulted into a two-fold increase of both peak height and area (8.7 V vs. 17 V and 140 Vs vs. 280 Vs, respectively). **Figure 3B** shows that modifying the rate of the Ar gas flow which transports Hg from the Hydra IIc to the MC-ICP-MS unit (“sample gas”), within the limited modifications permitted by the mass flow controller incorporated into the Hydra IIc unit (between 0.20 L min^{-1} and 0.30 L min^{-1}), does not significantly impact the peak profile. However, better plasma stability was observed with a gas flow rate of 0.2 L min^{-1} , resulting in fewer disturbances associated with abrupt changes in gas flow rates. **Figure 3C** shows that the peak width tends to increase at higher desorption temperatures ($600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ vs. $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). As acquiring more data points could provide an improvement in isotope ratio precision [32], a desorption temperature of $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was selected.

Figure 3. Effect of the (A) Hg concentration, (B) sample gas flow rate, and (C) desorption temperature on the peak intensity and peak profile. (printed in B/W in the printed journal)

Figure 4 provides an example of the Hg and Tl signals obtained via MC-ICP-MS instrumentation using the Hydra IIc as a sample introduction system after method optimization. Transient signals were obtained for $^{198-202}\text{Hg}^+$ (introduction via Hydra IIc), while the $^{203,205}\text{Tl}^+$ signals were continuous (introduction via pneumatic nebulization). A measurement window of approximately 60 seconds was necessary to capture the signal, with the transient Hg signal lasting for approximately 40 seconds (approx. 15 seconds and 25 seconds at 10% and 50% of the peak height, respectively). As shown in **Figure 4** and the corresponding figure inset, appropriate gas flow matching was achieved, as evidenced by the very similar Tl signal intensity before and after turning V3 to the “on” position. Following signal monitoring, the valves were returned to their original positions (“off”).

Figure 4. Example of transient $^{198-202}\text{Hg}^+$ peak profiles generated by the Hg^0 coming from the Hydra IIc unit and the continuous $^{203,205}\text{Tl}^+$ signals resulting from the Tl aerosol produced via pneumatic nebulization. (printed in B/W in the printed journal)

3.2. Method development for isotopic analysis of Hg using the Hydra IIc and MC-ICP-MS combination

To ensure accurate and precise isotope ratio measurements, it was crucial to prevent cross-contamination between samples when using the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS combination, which could potentially be related to the sample boats or amalgamation system. Various sequences were tested to assess carry-over between consecutive samples. Before each analysis, the Ni sample boats underwent pre-cleaning using the same program as that used for sample analysis. Following proper cleaning, sequences of different durations with and without intercalating blank measurements were evaluated for minimizing Hg memory effects. The best performance was observed with a short “5-sample” analysis sequence consisting of analyzing two consecutive blanks (for the first blank 100 μL of ultrapure water absorbed onto diatomaceous earth was introduced into the boat, while for the second blank, an empty boat was used) before every standard-sample-standard measurement (SSB approach). **Figure 5** illustrates that without such cleaning sequence, the results increasingly deviate from the expected $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ values, thus suggesting the occurrence of Hg memory effects.

Figure 5 clearly demonstrates that including the aforementioned cleaning sequence reliably corrects for this trend, enabling accurate isotope ratio results to be obtained, albeit at the cost of an increase in the analysis time. It is noteworthy that the $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ results reported in **Figure 5** for the in-house standard solution of Hg were corrected for mass bias using external correction in an SSB approach only, and that the linear regression slope approach was employed for data treatment of transient Hg signals (see below).

Figure 5. $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ signal monitoring to assess the effect of including a cleaning sequence. The error bars represent the standard error of the slope using the LRS method. The solid and dashed lines represent the average $\pm 2\text{SD}$ of the previously obtained IH value [16]. When a cleaning sequence is not used, each measurement replicate ($\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ value) involves three measurements: NIST – IH – NIST. However, with a cleaning sequence, each measurement replicate requires five measurements: two blanks – NIST – IH – NIST. (printed in B/W in the printed journal)

Once the optimum measurement sequence was established, the accuracy and precision of the method developed were assessed by analyzing a previously characterized in-house standard solution of Hg. Various data treatment approaches for obtaining Hg isotope ratio values from the transient signals obtained using

the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS set-up were evaluated, *i.e.*, point-by-point (PbP) evaluation, peak area integration (PAI), and the linear regression slope approach (LRS). A short description of the different data treatment strategies is provided in the Supplementary Material. The results obtained for the measurement of five replicates of the IH standard solution are summarized in **Table 3**. ANOVA analysis at a 95% level of significance indicates no significant variation between the results obtained using the three different data treatment approaches ($F_{\text{experimental}} < F_{\text{critical}}$). Additionally, good agreement between the results obtained with the three different data treatment approaches and the reference values was observed in all cases ($t_{\text{experimental}} < t_{\text{critical}}$). Despite the outcome of the statistical evaluation, a slight improvement in precision was observed for the PAI and LRS approaches compared to the PbP approach. Based on these results, both the PAI and LRS approaches were deemed most suited for data treatment of the transient signals originating from the use of the Hydra IIc as a sample introduction system for MC-ICP-MS. LRS was selected for further data treatment throughout this work, as this methodology has also been chosen in other studies on Hg isotopic analysis based on transient signals [27, 28].

Table 3. Comparison of the $\delta^{\text{xxx}}\text{Hg}$ (‰) values for the IH standard obtained with three different data treatment strategies, alongside the reference values. The uncertainty is expressed as the standard deviation of five measurement replicates.

		$\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$ (‰)	$\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (‰)
Data treatment approach	Point by point	-0.20 ± 0.18	-0.24 ± 0.06	-0.48 ± 0.08	-0.55 ± 0.07
	Peak area integration	-0.17 ± 0.11	-0.27 ± 0.03	-0.48 ± 0.06	-0.56 ± 0.04
	Linear regression slope	-0.16 ± 0.09	-0.27 ± 0.04	-0.48 ± 0.08	-0.57 ± 0.05
Literature values	Rua-Ibarz et al. [16]	-0.14 ± 0.09	-0.30 ± 0.12	-0.45 ± 0.12	-0.59 ± 0.15

3.3. Analysis of solid CRMs using the newly developed Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS method

For proof-of-concept, isotopic analysis of Hg was carried out for CRMs for which the corresponding reference values are available. Efficient extraction of Hg from the solid sample and its transfer to the MC-

ICP-MS instrument for analysis must be achieved without additional isotope fractionation compared to the aqueous external standard used for mass bias correction (NIST SRM 3133). In addition, sample heterogeneity may be more relevant with the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS method, as the amount of sample consumed is considerably lower compared to CVG-MC-ICP-MS after sample digestion (>500 mg). Additionally, the amount of standard required for adequate mass bias correction depends on the Hg concentration in the samples of interest. These aspects were evaluated in this work by analyzing two solid CRMs of biological origin with quite different (20-fold) Hg concentration levels: NCR-CNRC TORT-3 (Lobster hepatopancreas, $0.292 \pm 0.022 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) and BCR CRM 464 (Tuna fish, $5.25 \pm 0.10 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$). With a sample mass of 65 mg and 7.5 mg, respectively, the absolute Hg intake corresponded to approximately 20 ng and 40 ng Hg, respectively.

In this work, the results obtained using external correction based on an SSB approach were compared with those obtained after internal correction using the Russell law in combination with external correction in an SSB approach (double correction). It is important to remark that in this specific setup, the Tl isotopic standard (NIST SRM 997) was continuously introduced, while the way in which Hg was introduced resulted in transient signals. **Table 4** shows the $\delta^{199-202}\text{Hg}$ and $\Delta^{199,201}\text{Hg}$ values obtained for the BCR-464 and TORT-3 certified reference materials (n=5). At a 95% level of significance, no differences were found between the results obtained using external (SSB) correction only and the combination of internal (Russell) and external (SSB) correction ($t_{\text{experimental}} < t_{\text{critical}}$). Additionally, good agreement was found between the results obtained in this work using the newly developed method and those reported in the literature. This further demonstrates the capabilities of the newly developed approach for obtaining accurate and precise Hg isotope ratio results from solid samples without the need for matrix-matching for correction for instrumental mass discrimination.

Table 4. Hg isotopic composition of the CRMs analyzed in this work and the comparison with previously reported data. The uncertainty is expressed as the standard deviation of five measurement replicates.

		TORT-3					
		$\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$	$\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$	$\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$	$\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$	$\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$	$\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$
		(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)
This study	SSB	0.46 ± 0.11	-0.11 ± 0.06	0.10 ± 0.02	-0.47 ± 0.15	0.57 ± 0.15	0.40 ± 0.12
	SSB+Russell	0.48 ± 0.14	-0.08 ± 0.06	0.14 ± 0.10	-0.34 ± 0.08	0.57 ± 0.15	0.40 ± 0.12
Literature values	Rua-Ibarz et al. [6]	0.58 ± 0.02	-0.13 ± 0.10	0.26 ± 0.16	-0.30 ± 0.05	0.65 ± 0.02	0.49 ± 0.08
	Rua-Ibarz et al. [16]	0.57 ± 0.10	-0.17 ± 0.12	0.14 ± 0.10	-0.47 ± 0.18	0.68 ± 0.14	0.50 ± 0.12
	Rua-Ibarz et al. [37]	---	---	---	-0.30 ± 0.07	0.63 ± 0.09	0.49 ± 0.09
	Bolea-Fernandez et al. [38]	---	---	---	-0.18 ± 0.05	0.54 ± 0.01	0.51 ± 0.09
		BCR CRM 464					
		$\delta^{199}\text{Hg}$	$\delta^{200}\text{Hg}$	$\delta^{201}\text{Hg}$	$\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$	$\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$	$\Delta^{201}\text{Hg}$
		(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)
This study	SSB	2.47 ± 0.06	0.42 ± 0.13	2.40 ± 0.15	0.65 ± 0.18	2.30 ± 0.03	1.91 ± 0.02
	SSB+Russell	2.42 ± 0.05	0.34 ± 0.08	2.27 ± 0.13	0.48 ± 0.17	2.30 ± 0.03	1.91 ± 0.02
Literature values	Rua-Ibarz et al. [6]	2.16 ± 0.08	0.38 ± 0.06	2.15 ± 0.06	0.63 ± 0.03	2.00 ± 0.05	1.68 ± 0.04
	Berail et al. [15]	2.34 ± 0.29	0.33 ± 0.25	2.23 ± 0.27	0.58 ± 0.23	---	---
	Rua-Ibarz et al. [16]	2.09 ± 0.19	0.35 ± 0.20	2.05 ± 0.18	0.56 ± 0.20	1.95 ± 0.16	1.63 ± 0.18
	Epov et al. [32]	2.33 ± 0.11	0.37 ± 0.14	2.23 ± 0.18	0.59 ± 0.20	2.18 ± 0.08	1.79 ± 0.08
	Laffont et al. [33]	2.24 ± 0.07	0.19 ± 0.15	2.01 ± 0.06	0.27 ± 0.20	2.20 ± 0.03	1.82 ± 0.05
	Perrot et al. [34]	2.02 ± 0.27	0.33 ± 0.03	1.96 ± 0.21	0.55 ± 0.06	1.88 ± 0.26	1.54 ± 0.20
	Sherman et al. [35]	2.57 ± 0.08	0.43 ± 0.05	2.48 ± 0.03	0.68 ± 0.06	2.40 ± 0.02	1.97 ± 0.07
	Masbou et al. [36]	2.48 ± 0.08	0.50 ± 0.14	2.47 ± 0.14	0.73 ± 0.14	2.29 ± 0.09	1.92 ± 0.04
	Rua-Ibarz et al. [37]	---	---	---	0.52 ± 0.09	2.14 ± 0.12	1.76 ± 0.13
	Bolea-Fernandez et al. [38]	---	---	---	0.44 ± 0.07	2.09 ± 0.05	1.72 ± 0.03

4. Conclusions

In this work, a novel methodology for the direct isotopic analysis of solid samples containing low concentrations of Hg (20-40 ng Hg absolute amounts) was developed. This new approach involved coupling a commercially available Hg combustion analyzer (Hydra IIc) with an MC-ICP-MS instrument. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this on-line combination of both instruments has not been reported in the literature before.

After hardware modification and optimization of the instrument settings, accurate and precise Hg isotope ratio results were obtained for a previously characterized in-house standard solution of Hg and

two certified reference materials of biological origin with a 20-fold difference in their Hg concentration levels, without any sample pretreatment. The linear regression slope approach was used for handling the transient signals and mass discrimination was adequately corrected for by external (SSB) correction only or the combination of internal (Russell) and external (SSB) correction, without the need of matrix-matching (SSB of a solid sample vs. the NIST SRM 3133 aqueous standard). This initial validation demonstrates that this approach is promising for direct isotopic analysis of Hg in samples characterized by either low sample amounts or analyte concentrations.

Author contributions

EBF: Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; Validation; Visualization; Writing - original draft; and Writing - review & editing.

ARI: Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; Validation; Visualization; Writing - review & editing.

JAA: Methodology; Software.

FV: Conceptualization; Funding acquisition; Project administration; Resources; Supervision; Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest. The Hydra IIc unit was made available to the research team by Teledyne Leeman Labs.

Data availability

Data will be made available upon request.

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Supplementary Material

Development and initial evaluation of a combustion-based sample introduction system for direct isotopic analysis of mercury in solid samples via multi-collector ICP-mass spectrometry

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Technical description of the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS combination

The three electrical valves were initially placed in position 1 (**Figure 2A**), with all valves switched to the “off” position. This prevented the entrance of combustion gases into the MC-ICP-MS instrument (V2), while supplying O₂ to the Hydra IIc (V1) and Ar to the ICP (V3). During this step, sample decomposition occurred at high temperature, and the Hg was collected through amalgamation with gold. After completion of the sample combustion and Hg trapping, the second step started during the waiting time of the Hydra IIc (**Figure 2B**). In this step, switching V1 to the “on” position initiated the purge of O₂ gas via sweeping with an Ar flow coming from the “Sample gas flow controller” of the Neptune *Plus* unit (approximately 0.20 L min⁻¹). At this stage, V2 and V3 remained in the “off” position, allowing the Hydra IIc to purge combustive gases through the exhaust exit connected to V2, preventing their entrance into the ICP. To ensure proper purging, the waiting time of the Hydra IIc was significantly extended in comparison with the typical conditions when using the Hydra IIc Hg analyzer as a stand-alone unit (from 30 to 120 seconds). In both steps 1 and 2, Ar was supplied to the ICP to maintain plasma stability and minimize changes when switching between gas sources. It is important to note that the total Ar gas flow rate, approximately 0.70 L min⁻¹, was sustained by mixing two different Ar gas flow rates using a T-piece. The “Spare 2 mass flow controller” of the Neptune unit provided 0.50 L min⁻¹ of Ar gas used for nebulizing a Tl standard solution, while 0.20 L min⁻¹ was introduced using the “Spare 1 mass flow controller” through V3 and mixed with the wet aerosol in the T-piece. This approach allowed for robust wet plasma conditions and for using Tl as internal standard to correct for instrumental mass discrimination. Changes in the Ar flow rates during the gas exchange would result into temporal plasma instability, and consequently, would jeopardize the reliability of the results. It is worth mentioning that gas flows were optimized to achieve maximum sensitivity, and slight differences were observed between measurement sessions. Furthermore, the O₂ gas flow controller of the Hydra IIc limited the introduction of a higher Ar gas flow rate through the system, which was compensated for by increasing the Spare 2 gas flow rate. After successful purging of the combustion gases, V2 and V3 were sequentially switched to the “on” position during the third step (**Figure 2C**), establishing the connection between both units and enabling the gas flow from the Hydra IIc to enter the ICP. During this step, the gas introduced into the ICP was governed by the Sample gas controller instead of the Spare 1 flow controller. Despite the challenging nature of this step, the plasma stability was not compromised during this gas switching phase. This can be attributed to the fast response of the electrical valves, thus assuring that no critical flow differences were observed during the gas-change due to adequate matching of the Ar gas flow rates. To study the effect of this phase on the plasma conditions, the signal intensity for Tl introduced via pneumatic nebulization was monitored throughout the different steps of the process. Once the connection between both instruments was established, Hg desorption commenced by heating of the amalgamator. Gaseous Hg⁰ was transported using the Ar flow and mixed with the wet aerosol containing the Tl internal standard produced via pneumatic nebulization. During this step, a transient Hg signal was obtained via AAS and MC-ICP-MS monitoring. After analyzing each sample, all valves were switched to the “off” positions again, thus restoring the initial conditions.

Figure S1. Graphic representation of the electronic configuration (A) and picture (B) of the setup allowing high-precision Hg isotopic analysis using the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS combination.

Figure S2. Linear correlation between the MC-ICP-MS signal intensity and the Hydra IIc absorbance.

Data treatment approaches

Various data treatment approaches for obtaining Hg isotope ratio values from the transient signals obtained using the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS set-up were evaluated. These approaches include the point-by-point (PbP), peak area integration (PAI), and linear regression slope (LRS) methods. The PbP method involves calculating the average isotope ratio based on the isotope ratios measured at several points within the peak profile (**Figure S3-A**). For the PAI approach, the isotope ratio is determined based on the integrated peak areas of the isotopes involved (**Figure S3-B**). The LRS approach relies on plotting the intensities at $m/z = 199, 200, 201,$ and 202 versus the intensity at $m/z = 198$. The slopes of the best-fitting lines through the data points correspond to the different Hg isotope ratios $^{199}\text{Hg}/^{198}\text{Hg}$, $^{200}\text{Hg}/^{198}\text{Hg}$, $^{201}\text{Hg}/^{198}\text{Hg}$, and $^{202}\text{Hg}/^{198}\text{Hg}$ (**Figure S3-C**).

Figure S3. Graphical representation of the different data treatment approaches for obtaining Hg isotope ratio values from the transient signals obtained using the Hydra IIc – MC-ICP-MS set-up. (A) Point-by-point (PbP), (B) peak area integration (PAI), and (C) linear regression slope approach.